

OXYFLUOBORATES AND THEIR CHEMICAL ANALOGY WITH SULPHATES PART II. OXYFLUOBORATES OF Cu, Zn, Cd, Co AND Ni

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The oxyfluoborates of copper, zinc cobalt, cadmium, and nickel have been prepared. This copper salt crystallises out with five molecules of water; Zn salt with 7, Co salt with 6 and 7, Ni salt with 7 and 6 and the Cd salt with $8/3$ molecules of water. All these compounds are highly soluble in water. Some of them are soluble also in 60% alcohol to a great extent. These compounds form mixed crystals with the corresponding sulphates. Some of these compounds are hygroscopic. These compounds decompose at a high temperature with evolution of boron trifluoride. The equivalent conductivities of zinc oxyfluoborate solutions reveal that in solution the compound affords only two ions Zn^{2+} and $BF_3O_3^-$. The solutions of these compounds give instantaneous precipitation with barium chloride and the precipitates are insoluble in hydrochloric acid.

In Part I of this series (*this issue*, p. 617) the structure of the oxyfluoborate ion has been discussed and in this connection it has been pointed out that the oxyfluoborates should exhibit resemblance with the corresponding sulphates in composition as well as in chemical properties. The oxyfluoborates of the alkali and the alkaline earth metals have been described before; the present paper deals with the methods of preparation and properties of the oxyfluoborates of other metals such as copper, zinc, cadmium, cobalt and nickel.

Other fluoride, oxyfluoride or hydroxyfluoride complex ions, behaving like the sulphate group, have been studied before (Ray, *Z. anorg. allgem. Chem.*, 1932, 206, 209; 1939, 241, 165; Lange, *Ber.*, 1927, 60, 962; 1928, 61, 799; Mitra, *this Journal*, 1956, 33, 45). The oxyfluoborates of the metals, mentioned above, differ from the corresponding fluoberyllates and monofluophosphates in being excessively soluble in water, and some of them are also highly soluble in 60% alcohol.

These hydrated salts resemble the corresponding sulphates in their composition as well as in their chemical properties. Even cadmium oxyfluoborate maintains its interesting property of crystallising with $8/3$ molecules of water.

EXPERIMENTAL

C. P. quality materials were used for the preparation of these compounds. The standard methods of analysis (Scott, "Standard Methods for Chemical Analysis", D. Van Nostrand Co., New York) were followed for the quantitative analysis of the respective constituents.

Copper Oxyfluoborate Pentahydrate, $CuBF_3O_3 \cdot 5H_2O$.—To copper carbonate (5.5 g.) containing about 57.5% of Cu, taken in a platinum basin and moistened with water, hydrofluoric acid (40%) was added cautiously to decompose all the carbonate. The resulting mass was then warmed on a water-bath for a few minutes in order to decompose the last traces of carbonates. About 25 c.c. of water was then added, followed by the addition of 3.1 g. of boric acid. The whole mixture

was digested on the water-bath till the boric acid dissolved. To this mixture 2.5 c.c. of 40% hydrofluoric acid was added according to the equation :

This mixture was digested on a water-bath for about 15 minutes and to it 12N-HNO₃ was added dropwise with stirring till almost a clear solution was obtained. To this solution approximately 25 c.c. of water was added, followed by a few drops of hydrofluoric acid. The whole mass was digested on the water-bath for about 1 hour. It was cooled to room temperature (30°), filtered and concentrated in a vacuum desiccator (H₂SO₄). The blue transparent crystals obtained after a few days were filtered under suction, washed quickly with 60% alcohol and dried between the folds of a filter paper. (Found: F, 23.90; Cu, 26.84; B, 4.50. CuBF₃O, 5H₂O requires F, 24.05; Cu, 26.38; B, 4.56%).

Copper oxyfluoborate is highly soluble in water and hygroscopic. It is also soluble in 60% alcohol. It formed mixed crystals with the corresponding sulphate. The X-ray diffraction study has, however, revealed that they are not isomorphous. (Das Gupta, Ray and Mitra, this *Journal*, 1958, 35, 185).

Nickel Oxyfluoborate Heptahydrate, NiBF₃O, 7H₂O.—Nickel carbonate (7 g.) containing nearly 42% of nickel, boric acid (3.1 g.) and 40% hydrofluoric acid (2.5 c.c.) were heated exactly in a similar way, as described before for the preparation of this compound. The green crystals obtained were washed with 60% alcohol and dried between the folds of a filter paper. (Found: F, 21.10; Ni, 21.82; B, 4.00. NiBF₃O, 7H₂O requires F, 21.23; Ni, 21.86; B, 4.03%).

This heptahydrated compound was obtained when the mother-liquor was allowed to concentrate at a low temperature. When the solution was allowed to concentrate on the water-bath, the green crystals were found to contain 23.20% of nickel. It may be suggested in keeping with the observations made before (Ray, *loc. cit.*; Mitra, *loc. cit.*) that this compound is hexahydrated nickel oxyfluoborate. (NiBF₃O, 6H₂O requires Ni, 23.42%).

Cobalt oxyfluoborate heptahydrate, CoBF₃O, 7H₂O was obtained as pink-coloured crystals. (Found: F, 21.38; Co, 21.78; B, 4.07. CoBF₃O, 7H₂O requires F, 21.20; Co, 21.98; B, 4.03%).

It is also highly soluble in water and on heating to 40° becomes blue in colour.

When a solution of heptahydrated cobalt oxyfluoborate was allowed to crystallise on a water-bath, the crystals were found to contain 23.28% of cobalt. Careful heating of the heptahydrated salt in the vicinity of 75° yielded the compound which was found to contain 23.28% of cobalt. These observations suggest that in both the cases the hexahydrated salts are formed. (CoBF₃O, 6H₂O requires Co, 23.50%).

As the preparation of the oxyfluoborates necessitated the addition of nitric acid, the ferrous oxyfluoborate could not be prepared.

Zinc oxyfluoborate heptahydrate, ZnBF₃O, 7H₂O, was obtained in the same way as the copper compound from zinc carbonate (5.7 g.) containing approximately

57.56% of zinc, boric acid (3.1 g.) and 40% hydrofluoric acid (2.5 c.c.). (Found: F, 20.53; Zn, 23.80; B, 3.92. $ZnBF_3O \cdot 7H_2O$ requires F, 20.70; Zn, 23.75; B, 3.93%.)

These white crystals are slightly hygroscopic and highly soluble in water. $ZnBF_3O \cdot 7H_2O$ was also prepared without the addition of nitric acid during the procedure; the yield was, however, very poor.

$ZnBF_3O \cdot 7H_2O$ was dissolved in water and the conductivity of the solutions at different concentrations was measured by the usual method.

TABLE I

Conc. of the soln.	M/32	M/64	M/128	M/256	M/1024
Conductivity	56	78	102	140	158

If it is considered that the equivalent conductivity at infinite dilution increases by about 2% per degree, λ_0 becomes approximately equal to 120 at 18°. At the same temperature $\lambda_0 = 130.1$ for KCl. The compound $ZnBF_3O$ therefore dissociates into two ions in solution according to the equation:

Cadmium oxyfluoborate 8/3 hydrate, $CdBF_3O \cdot 8/3 H_2O$ was prepared as above from cadmium carbonate (8.6 g.), boric acid (3.1 g.) and 40% HF (2.5 c.c.). (Found: F, 23.12; Cd, 45.74; B, 4.47. $CdBF_3O \cdot 8/3 H_2O$ requires F, 23.34; Cd, 46.03; B, 4.43%.)

This white salt is extremely hygroscopic and easily goes into solution in 60% alcohol.

All these soluble oxyfluoborates could be recrystallised from aqueous solutions. Hence BF_3O^{2-} ion is stable in solution and does not undergo any appreciable dissociation. They gave instantaneous precipitation with barium chloride solution. The white precipitate formed was insoluble in hydrochloric acid. These compounds when heated, started losing water molecules. No other hydrated forms could, however, be isolated in this investigation. At higher temperatures the compounds were found to decompose and BF_3 gas was evolved.

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